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Emotional Maturity, Gratitude, and Life Satisfaction: A Correlational Study among Young Adults

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Abstract

The research seeks to explore the relationship between emotional maturity, gratitude, and life satisfaction in young individuals. When we start discussing youth, it's essentially an age range in our lives where we face numerous challenges, and coping with these challenges can be quite difficult. As we talk about youth, this is a time period when significant physical, psychological, and social changes occur. In the context of positive psychology, life satisfaction is a crucial construct. Life satisfaction refers to our cognitive appraisal of how satisfied we are with our lives, encompassing physical, social, and emotional aspects. When we focus on youth, we observe that many are not happy with their health, experiencing physical abnormalities or mental struggles, particularly with their studies. They often feel challenged and unable to express themselves. This study aims to explore how emotional maturity can help individuals deal with life's challenges and cultivate gratitude for what they have, ultimately achieving life satisfaction.

Keywords Emotional maturity, Gratitude, Life satisfaction and Youth .

Introduction

Emotional maturity involves understanding and managing one's emotions effectively, rather than being overwhelmed by them. For instance, when faced with physical health issues during a critical moment, such as an exam, one should focus on finding solutions rather than getting bogged down by negative thoughts. In the context of youth, this age range is characterized by multiple distractions, including relationships, family dynamics, and academic pressures. Many young individuals may feel unsatisfied with their lives, struggling to find happiness and fulfillment. This study seeks to investigate how life satisfaction can be achieved by cultivating emotional maturity, gratitude, and a positive outlook, even in the face of challenges. By focusing on these aspects, young individuals can develop a more optimistic approach to life, leading to greater overall satisfaction. In India, where parental pressure and academic expectations are high, this study can provide valuable insights into the importance of emotional maturity, gratitude, and life satisfaction among youth. By exploring these constructs, we can better understand how to support young individuals in achieving happiness and fulfillment in their lives.

Objective of study

- 1.To explore the relationship between emotional maturity, gratitude, and life satisfaction in young individuals.
- 2.To determine the significant connection between emotional maturity and life satisfaction in youth.
- 3.To identify a significant relationship between gratitude and life satisfaction among young people.

Review of Literature

This chapter offers an overview of the current research surrounding emotional maturity, gratitude, and life satisfaction. Our examination indicates that emotional maturity and

gratitude are crucial positive elements that enhance overall life satisfaction and positively affect the psychological and emotional well-being of youth.

Chauhan et al. (2025) conducted a study utilizing a cross-sectional survey design and gathered data online. The results indicated a positive correlation between gratitude and life satisfaction, with gratitude identified as a significant predictor of life satisfaction. Additionally, mental well-being was found to mediate the relationship between gratitude and life satisfaction. These results imply that gratitude positively influences life satisfaction, mediated by mental well-being.

Singh, M., and Sharma, R. (2024) explored the relationship among childhood trauma, emotional maturity, and life satisfaction in university students. The research included 140 participants, comprising 70 males and 70 females, aged between 18 and 25 years. The findings indicated a negative relationship between childhood trauma and emotional maturity, as well as between childhood trauma and life satisfaction among college students. In addition, a positive relationship was observed between emotional maturity and life satisfaction. No significant differences were noted in childhood trauma or emotional maturity based on gender. However, a notable difference was observed in life satisfaction between male and female participants.

Christina et al. (2022) discovered that dedicating just 10 minutes a week to practicing gratitude can significantly impact the lives of high school students. It can enhance their life satisfaction, inspire them to pursue self-improvement, and foster deeper connections with others. This straightforward practice can lead to lasting improvements in their well-being.

Saji, A., & Simon, S. (202). In their research, a sample of 405 young adults was analyzed using convenience sampling techniques. The findings indicated a positive relationship between general well-being and both gratitude and life satisfaction. Furthermore, a notable difference in gratitude levels was found between males and females, with females showing greater levels of gratitude than males. This observation aligns with earlier studies that suggest females generally exhibit higher gratitude than males.

In 2021, Gulia Pooja carried out a study examining the connection between gratitude and life satisfaction in young adults. The participant group comprised 110 individuals aged 18-25, with an equal distribution of males and females. The outcomes revealed significant variations in gratitude and life satisfaction between genders, where women demonstrated more gratitude, while men reported greater life satisfaction. Additionally, a positive association was found between gratitude and life satisfaction among adults.

In 2020, researchers Yanhui Xiang and Rong Yuan examined the connection between dispositional gratitude and life satisfaction in a sample of 991 Chinese students. Their findings revealed that both benign envy and malicious envy, along with mindfulness, influenced this relationship.

In a study carried out in 2018, Geeta explored the links between emotional maturity, emotional intelligence, and life satisfaction in female college students. A total of 60 girls aged between 17 and 24 years were assessed. The findings indicated a positive correlation between emotional maturity and life satisfaction. Interestingly, no significant connection was discovered between emotional intelligence and life satisfaction, nor between emotional intelligence and emotional maturity.

Main Text

Life Satisfaction

Life satisfaction is a highly personal and subjective experience that can vary significantly from one individual to another. What constitutes satisfaction for one person may not hold the same value for another, making it challenging to define objectively. Ultimately, life satisfaction is a unique and individualized experience that differs from person to person.

Life satisfaction theories

There are two types of theories which is about life satisfaction 1.Bottom-uptheories 2. Top down theories

1. Bottom-up theories:

Bottom-up theories of life satisfaction propose that overall life satisfaction is derived from the aggregation of satisfaction in specific life domains, including work, health, economic

conditions, and others. This approach suggests that life satisfaction is a cumulative outcome of our experiences and evaluations in these distinct areas.

2. Top-down theories:

When we discuss top-down theories of life satisfaction, according to these theories, our overall life satisfaction has a cascading effect on our satisfaction in specific life domains. According to this approach, our general life satisfaction sets the tone for how we evaluate and experience satisfaction in particular areas, indicating that our overall life satisfaction plays a defining role in shaping our satisfaction in specific domains.

Emotional maturity

Emotional maturity refers to the ability to comprehend, manage, and communicate emotions in a way that fosters healthy relationships and personal development.

Components of emotional maturity

When discussing the components of emotional maturity,

The first component is managing emotions. Managing emotions refers to the ability to use our emotions in a healthy and productive way, both in the present moment and beyond.

The second component is expression. Expressing emotions healthily means using our emotions in a way that is not disruptive or harmful, but rather productive and thoughtful.

The third component is taking responsibility. When we feel an emotion in the present moment, we should take responsibility for it ourselves, rather than blaming others or making them responsible for our emotions.

The fourth component is building strong relationships. Emotional intelligence is essential for building and maintaining healthy relationships with others.

The fifth component is resilience and coping. When we can use our emotions in a healthy way, we are better able to cope with adversity and traumatic events in our lives.

The sixth element is self-awareness, which involves recognizing and comprehending our own feelings, such as our moods and emotional conditions.

The seventh element is empathy, which entails the capacity to acknowledge and understand the emotions of those around us and to leverage this understanding to foster stronger connections.

Importance of emotional maturity for youth:

Emotional maturity is essential for the well-being of young individuals. It helps alleviate stress and fosters emotional balance, ultimately contributing to better mental health.

Furthermore, emotional maturity enables young people to develop healthy relationships by understanding their own emotions and empathizing with others. This capacity for emotional intelligence is vital for building and maintaining strong, positive relationships.

Emotional maturity plays a significant role in enhancing our decision-making abilities. By understanding and managing our emotions effectively, we can think more critically and make more informed decisions. This emotional intelligence enables us to approach situations with a clearer mind, fostering creative thinking and ultimately leading to better decision-making outcomes.

Emotional maturity plays a significant role in facilitating personal growth. By constructively processing our past emotions, we can extract valuable lessons from our experiences and apply them to enhance our present and future. This introspection enables us to make informed decisions, leading to a more purposeful and effective life trajectory. By leveraging our past experiences, we can create a brighter, more successful future.

Emotional maturity is a vital factor in determining academic success, especially during the formative years of youth. As young individuals navigate the challenges of education and career development, emotional maturity enables them to approach obstacles with a level head, manage their emotions, and make informed decisions. By doing so, they can learn from setbacks, stay focused on their goals, and ultimately achieve greater academic success.

Gratitude

Gratitude is a Latin word that originates from the Latin word "grates," meaning "thankful" and "pleasing". In psychology, gratitude is a positive emotional response that an individual experiences when they receive kindness, love, and benefits from others. We consider gratitude as both a state and a trait in psychology.

As a trait, gratitude refers to an individual's general ability to express thankful to others when they receive something. This ability enables them to show kindness and love towards others. As a state, gratitude is defined as a specific emotional experience that occurs when an individual feels pleased and thankful in response to a particular action or gesture.

A major aspect of gratitude is the recognition of goodness. Gratitude begins when we recognize that what others have given us is a gift, not something we deserve. This recognition helps us appreciate the kindness of others and feel thankful for their actions.

Another aspect of gratitude is the acknowledgement of external sources. We must accept that our positive emotions and experiences are often the result of external factors, such as the actions of others, rather than our own efforts alone.

The psychological effects of gratitude on youth are significant. When young people practice gratitude, it can increase their well-being, enhance their relationships, and reduce negative emotions. By focusing on the things they are thankful for, young people can develop a more positive outlook and appreciate the good things in their lives.

Research has also shown that regular gratitude practice can have physical health benefits, such as improved sleep quality and overall physical well-being. In contrast, individuals who do not practice gratitude may experience poorer physical health.

Rationale

Youth is a critical stage in an individual's life, marked by numerous psychological, social, and physical challenges. At this stage, emotionally mature decision-making is crucial, as the choices made can significantly impact one's entire life. Moreover, individuals are more vulnerable to feelings of dissatisfaction with their lives. Positive psychology constructs, such as gratitude and emotional maturity, can increase an individual's chances of feeling satisfied with their life. These positive traits enable individuals to survive in various conditions and improve their overall well-being and psychological health. While numerous studies have explored life satisfaction, there is a scarcity of research on the combined effects of emotional maturity and gratitude on overall life satisfaction. This is particularly relevant in countries like India, where youth are experiencing high levels of career-related dissatisfaction, leading to increased rates of suicidal attempts. The stigma associated with seeking help can exacerbate this issue, leading individuals to develop a mental ability that can culminate in suicidal tendencies. This study aims to explore how positive traits, such as emotional maturity and gratitude, can serve as a booster and strong pillar in times of need, ultimately improving life satisfaction. The findings of this study can inform interventions in educational, health, and developmental areas, enabling the enhancement of positive qualities and improvement of life satisfaction among youth. By focusing on the development of emotional maturity and gratitude, it is possible to create a more supportive environment that fosters overall well-being and psychological health.

Emotional Maturity Scale (Dr. Yashvir Singh and Dr. Mahesh Bhargava, 1994). It is a self-assessing five-point scale. The measure has 40 declarative statements, accompanied by five answer alternatives ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. This scale assesses five primary dimensions of emotional maturity: emotional instability, emotional regression, social adjustment capabilities, independent deficiency, and flexibility and adaptability. The highest attainable score is 200, while the lowest is 40. A lower score indicates superior emotional maturity, while a higher number signifies less emotional maturity. The scale has a reliability coefficient of 0.84, ascertained by the split-half technique with a sample size of 200 participants.

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Gratitude Questionnaire-6 Gray et al. (2002): The Gratitude Questionnaire-6, developed by Gray, Emmons, and Morrison in 2002, is a six-item questionnaire that assesses individual differences in gratitude experiences. Respondents rate each item on a 7-point scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). Higher scores indicate a higher level of gratitude.

Satisfaction with Life Scale Diener et al.,1999):

The Satisfaction with Life Scale, created by Diener, Suh, Lucas, and Smith in 1999, consists of five self-report items designed to evaluate a person's overall satisfaction with life. Judgments about life satisfaction reflect the cognitive aspect of subjective well-being, which is often known as happiness.

Methodology

Statement of Research Problem

The present research aims to study the association between Emotional maturity, Gratitude and Life satisfaction among Youth.

Procedure

This research aimed to investigate the correlation among emotional maturity, thankfulness, and life happiness in young individuals. We collected data using online surveys administered to individuals aged 18 to 25, selected via a purposive sample method. The instruments used for data collection included the Emotional Maturity Scale developed by Dr. Yashvir Singh and Dr. Mahesh Bhargava (1994), the Gratitude Questionnaire by Gray, Emmons, and Morrison (2002), and the Life Satisfaction Scale by Diener, Suh, Lucas, and Smith (1999). Before the questionnaires were distributed, participants received comprehensive information and had the opportunity to ask questions for better understanding. After collecting the data, it was scored and analyzed using SPSS software, with the findings being interpreted accordingly.

Sampling

A sample of 100 youth within the age range of 18-25 years. Out of 100, 50 males and 50 females were included in this study. The sample was selected through purposive sampling.

Result and Discussion

Result

H1: There will be a significant association between Emotional maturity and life satisfaction among youth.

Table-1: Descriptive Statistics Between Emotional Maturity and Life satisfaction among youth

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Emotional maturity	18.32	4.12
Life satisfaction	23.45	6.042

The present study was conducted on a sample of 100, divided equally between males and females, emerging adults aged 18-25 years. Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation for emotional maturity and life satisfaction.

Table 2: Correlation between Emotional maturity and Life satisfaction among youth

Variables	Sample size (N)	Correlation Coefficient (r)	P - value	Significance
Emotional maturity and Life satisfaction	100	0.59	P < 0.05	Statistically Significant (Positive correlation)

**In this study, a significant correlation is found at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

To examine the relationship between variables, product moment correlation was utilized. It was proposed that there would be a notable connection between emotional maturity and life satisfaction among young people. This proposal was corroborated by the findings presented in Table 2. The analysis showed a strong, statistically significant positive correlation between the two variables, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.59$ at ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that the relationship is not only robust but also highly improbable to have occurred by mere chance.

H2 : There will be a significant association between Gratitude and Life satisfaction among youth.

Table 3 : Descriptive Statistics Between Gratitude and Life satisfaction among youth

Variables	Means	Std Deviation
Gratitude	28.13	5.023
Life satisfaction	23.45	6.042

The present study was conducted on a sample of 100 divided equally as males and females emerging adults of age group 18-25 years. The table 1 shows mean and standard deviation for emotional maturity and life satisfaction.

Table 4: Correlation between Gratitude and Life satisfaction among youth

Variables	Sample size (N)	Correlation Coefficient (r)	P - value	Significance
Gratitude and Life satisfaction	100	0.64	P < 0.05	Statistically Significant (Positive correlation)

**In this study, a significant correlation is found at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

We used Pearson correlation analysis to examine the relationship between variables. A significant association between thankfulness and life satisfaction in young people has been proposed. Table 4 supports this hypothesis by showing a statistically significant correlation between thankfulness and life satisfaction in young people. The findings revealed a statistically significant positive link between thankfulness and life happiness, with a correlation value of $r = 0.64$ ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

Life satisfaction significantly influences an individual's comprehensive growth, including physical, mental, and social aspects. Fostering appreciation in one's life may improve life satisfaction, enabling people to overcome challenges and advance toward their objectives. Gratitude involves valuing all facets of existence, promoting self-sufficiency, and acknowledging one's strengths.

Emotional maturity is the capacity to comprehend and adeptly manage our emotions in several contexts, both in our surroundings and personal experiences. When adolescents master the regulation and efficient utilization of their emotions, they may enhance their academic achievements and their interpersonal relationships, familial interactions, friendships, and social affiliations.

A robust support system, whether family or social, empowers people to manage life's problems and enhance overall life happiness more effectively. Emotional maturity enables people to comprehend and regulate their thoughts and emotions, enhancing all facets of life. Consequently, emotional maturity is an essential competency for young persons, facilitating their success across several domains of life.

Parents and educators must cultivate appreciation in children, in conjunction with intellectual and social attributes, to guarantee whole growth. This research underscores the significance of thankfulness in enhancing happiness and general well-being, fostering a well-rounded person and, eventually, a developed society.

The present study investigated the correlation between adolescents' emotional development, thankfulness, and life satisfaction. One hundred individuals were surveyed, including 50 men and 50 girls aged between 18 and 25. Life pleasure has attracted much focus recently, especially among young individuals. As this group confronts the obstacles of moving into adulthood, comprehending the elements that influence their general well-being and life satisfaction has become more vital. Research indicates that several psychological and emotional elements significantly influence happiness, including appreciation and emotional maturity. This study investigated the relationships among adolescents' thankfulness, emotional maturity, and life satisfaction. Using product-moment correlation, the investigation demonstrated a robust, statistically significant positive association between emotional maturity and life satisfaction, shown by a correlation value of $r = 0.59$ ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that enhanced emotional maturity correlates with increased life satisfaction. The findings indicated a statistically significant positive link between thankfulness and life happiness, with a correlation value of $r = 0.64$ ($p < 0.05$). This signifies a robust and substantial correlation, indicating that elevated

thankfulness is linked to increased life satisfaction. These results are significant for comprehending the elements influencing young people's lives. The robust positive connections indicate that thankfulness and emotional maturity influence life's happiness. Consequently, treatments and tactics designed to foster appreciation and emotional maturity may effectively enhance life satisfaction in kids. By cultivating these attributes, people and organizations might enhance general well-being and life satisfaction among youngsters. The study's findings align with prior research, emphasizing the significance of thankfulness and emotional maturity in enhancing happiness. The results indicate that fostering thankfulness and emotional maturity is crucial for young individuals to attain greater happiness. Consequently, educators, mental health practitioners, and policymakers may use these results to guide the creation of treatments and programs designed to enhance life happiness in kids.

Nonetheless, the research had drawbacks. The research sample was rather small and had little variety. Furthermore, the online gathering of data presents an additional challenge since it fails to ensure the legitimacy of the replies. The research examines the correlation between emotional maturity, thankfulness, and life happiness without considering gender differences.

Notwithstanding these constraints, the research highlights the importance of thankfulness in enhancing life satisfaction and well-being. Subsequent studies may expand on these results by investigating methods to nurture thankfulness and promote comprehensive development in people.

In conclusion, gratitude plays a vital role in an individual's life, particularly during youth. By cultivating gratitude, young people can develop a more positive and appreciative mindset, leading to greater overall satisfaction with life.

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